

Molecular and System-Level Advances in Zinc/Organic Hybrid Redox Flow Batteries

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ABSTRACT

Redox flow batteries (RFBs) are gaining attention as a promising solution for large-scale renewable energy storage, essential for the continuous distribution of electricity. Although vanadium RFBs are gaining commercial traction, their deployment is constrained by high costs, the use of corrosive electrolytes, and the criticality of vanadium. The use of organic molecules as electro-active materials addresses sustainability challenges while offering enhanced versatility. Their molecular structure can be tailored to optimized performance, enabling their application in both aqueous and non-aqueous electrolytes. Among organic RFBs, Zinc/Organic hybrid RFBs have gained significant attention over the past decade as cost-effective, safe, and sustainable alternative to vanadium RFB for future scalable energy storage, combining abundant and scalable zinc negolytes with versatile organic posolytes. However, challenges such as hydrogen evolution, dendrite formation, pH dependency in electrochemical reactions, and limitations on operable current density hinder the performance of these batteries. This review critically examines the advancements in aqueous, non-aqueous, and membrane-free Zn/Organic RFBs, focusing on electrolyte chemistry, cell design, and performance optimization. It provides key insights into functionalization strategies of organic posolytes, the electrochemical stability of RFB, and emerging membrane-free biphasic systems, highlighting pathways to enhance cycle life, increase energy density, and reduce battery cost. Overall, this review offers perspectives on current research and future directions for developing cost-effective, high-performance Zn/Organic hybrid RFBs for sustainable energy storage.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

AORFB Aqueous organic redox flow battery
BESS Battery energy storage system
Cryo-EM Cryogenic electron microscopy
CV Cyclic voltammetry
DFT Density functional theory
DLS Dynamic light scattering
DOE Department of Energy
EIS Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy
EPR Electron paramagnetic resonance
ESI-MS Electrospray ionization mass spectra
ESS Energy storage system
FT-IR Fourier transform-infrared
HER Hydrogen evolution reaction

MD Molecular dynamics
ML Machine Learning
NMR Nuclear magnetic resonance
OCV Open circuit voltage
PHS Pumped hydroelectric storage
RAFT Reversible addition-fragmentation chain transfer
RFB Redox flow battery
SCE Saturated calomel electrode
SEM Scanning electron microscope
SHE Standard hydrogen electrode
SOC State of Charge
STEM Scanning transmission electron microscopy
TEMPO (2,2,6,6-Tetramethylpiperidin-1-yl) oxyl
TPA Triphenylamine
UV-Vis Ultraviolet-visible

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VRFB Vanadium redox flow battery
XRD X-ray diffraction

1. Introduction

1.1. Background on RFB

Rising energy demands and the need to reduce carbon footprints are becoming unsustainable due to fossil fuel depletion [1,2]. Renewable sources like solar and wind offer low-cost alternatives but face efficiency challenges from climatic fluctuations [3,4]. Large-scale energy storage systems (ESS) are crucial to bridging supply-demand gaps, with technologies such as pumped hydroelectric storage (PHS), battery energy storage systems (BESS), compressed air, and flywheels. While PHS (US\$ 0.061/kWh in 2022) is cost-effective [5],[6], it faces geographical and environmental constraints [7]. BESS (US\$ 56/kWh projected in 2024) offers flexibility but struggles with battery instability and fire hazards due to flammable electrolytes [8],[9].

Redox flow batteries (RFBs) are considered as realistic candidates for energy storage in the range of several kW/kWh up to tens of MW/MWh and have demonstrated appreciable progress in deployment as a technology for long-duration energy storage [10]. The innate advantage of RFB technology is the flexibility in configuring the system by means of decoupling power and energy density. Moreover, other characteristics such as the quick response time, sizing, cost, and reduced carbon footprint aids in its utilization [11]. Vanadium-based RFBs (VRFBs) are well developed and have already been commercialized with an energy density of 20 – 30 Wh L⁻¹ [12]. Nonetheless, less abundance, critical nature and the scarcity of vanadium active species along with the use of costly Nafion® membranes has driven their system capital costs beyond US\$ 300 per kWh, much higher than United States Department of Energy (DOE) target of US\$ 150 per kWh [13],[14].

Organic RFBs either employ small redox-active organic molecules or polymers as electro-active species, which can act as both polysolite and

negolyte [15],[16],[17],[18]. Organic RFBs offer cost advantages over VRFBs due to the potential for lower raw material costs, while also enabling competitive electrochemical performance. Beyond cost and performance, organic RFBs provide intrinsic benefits such as improved safety (lower toxicity and reduced fire risk), tunability through molecular design, and enhanced sustainability by using abundant, non-metallic, and potentially biodegradable materials. A diverse range of organics, including quinones, bipyridines, nitroxyl radicals, and ferrocenes, has been explored over the years, demonstrating energy densities up to 50 Wh L⁻¹ [19],[20],[21],[22]. Furthermore, significant progress has been made in cycling stability, with reports achieving up to 18000 charge-discharge cycles (62 days) with a low capacity decay of about 0.00029% cycle⁻¹ [23]. Although organic RFBs might offer high energy density, extended discharge durations, and significant long-term stability, their scalability remains a challenge. This limitation is primarily due to the high synthetic costs of electro-active materials. Many of these materials exceed DOE target molecular weight of 150 g mol⁻¹ per electron transferred, along with higher costs of electro-active materials, such as approximately US\$ 564 per kg for an organic molecule based on TEMPO (2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidin-1-yl)oxyl [24],[25].

Different from conventional RFB, hybrid RFBs operate through a liquid-solid redox transformation using a metal-based negative electrode/electrolyte, where metal ions in the electrolyte are reduced to metal (plating) and re-dissolve into the electrolyte during battery discharging (stripping) [26],[27]. Zinc-based hybrid RFBs are scientifically and industrially attractive due to zinc's non-critical status, abundance, availability in the Earth's crust, and affordability, with a cost less than US\$ 4 per kg [28],[29]. The Zinc-bromine hybrid RFBs was among the first to achieve market penetration, accounting for 40% of grid-connected projects worldwide [30]. Additionally, it employs a cost-effective microporous membrane, enhancing its economic viability [31]. Yet, excessively corrosive and toxic bromine electrolytes and the instability of the bromine complex during cycling remain critical issues [32],[33].

Figure 1. A representative schematic illustrating the background in RFB and the motivation for this review on Zn/Organic hybrid RFBs.

Figure 2. A schematic representing the different types of Zn/Organic RFBs analysed in this review – aqueous (Section 3), non-aqueous (Section 4) and membrane-free (Section 5).

The alkaline Zinc-Ferricyanide RFB was seen as a low-cost, sustainable alternative due to the abundance of zinc and non-toxic $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}/[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ redox couple. However, its performance was limited by low operational currents ($<35 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$) [34]. Additionally, poor ferro-ferricyanide solubility in basic media ($<0.4 \text{ M}$) and the high cost of Nafion® membranes hindered its energy density and commercial viability [35]. Cheng and co-workers proposed a Zinc-Nickel RFB with a single-flow and membrane-free configuration [36]. During charging, zincate ions were plated onto the negative electrode, while $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$ in the positive electrode was oxidized to NiOOH . As the electrode serves as the energy storage medium for both positive and negative redox processes, this battery does not achieve the decoupling of energy and power. Self-discharge was a major issue in these batteries, primarily caused by the corrosion of the Zn anode in the highly alkaline electrolyte ($>7 \text{ M KOH}$) [37]. Alternative hybrid RFBs were developed by incorporating Zn-metal electrodeposition with Cerium. A pilot scale Zinc-Cerium RFB operated by Plurion Inc. utilized a titanium sheet as the negative electrode and platinumized titanium mesh as the positive electrode, separated by a Nafion® membrane [38]. The electrolytes consisted of Zn^{2+} and Ce^{3+} , with methanesulfonic acid as the supporting electrolyte. Given the expensive materials used for the anode, cathode, and membrane, this system lacked cost competitiveness.

1.2. Motivation and Overview of the Review

To overcome the challenges associated with classical vanadium and

organic RFBs, as well as zinc-based inorganic RFBs, it was imperative to combine the benefits of a Zn-based negolyte with an organic posolyte (Figure 1). This presented a promising strategy for developing stable, high-capacity, and high-cell voltage RFBs with increased power density, while simultaneously achieving significant lower costs (US\$ 50 – 90 per kWh) than VRFBs [29],[39].

Over the years, numerous reviews have examined Zn-based hybrid redox flow batteries (RFBs), with most of the focus placed on inorganic and some organometallic posolytes [31],[40],[41],[42]. For instance, Zhu et al. provide a broad and thorough overview of RFBs, including fundamentals, material properties, applications, and key strategies to address system-level challenges [43]. Similarly, Zhao et al. present a focused review on recent advances in Zn-based RFBs, particularly emphasizing material-level improvements such as anode stabilization, cathode performance, membrane selectivity, and current collector optimization [44]. On the other hand, Pan et al. offer an in-depth review of organic redox-active materials for conventional aqueous organic RFBs (AORFBs), outlining key challenges and molecular design strategies with a strong emphasis on solubility and stability [45]. However, despite these valuable contributions, organic redox-active materials, particularly in the context of Zn/Organic RFBs, have received comparatively little attention. Taken together, these gaps highlight a clear need for a review that systematically examines the development, challenges, and future outlook of Zn/Organic hybrid RFBs. This review aims to address this gap by critically analyzing relevant studies on Zn/Organic hybrid RFBs, with a primary focus on organic posolytes, to differentiate and

Table 1
Performance metrics of redox flow batteries.

Attributes	Expression	Description
$U_{c,d}$ (V)*	$U_{c,d} = U_{OCV} \pm IR_{c,d}$	Cell Voltage – The potential difference between the negative and positive half cells of the flow battery
$i_{c,d}$ (mA cm ⁻²)*	$i_{c,d} = \frac{I}{A}$	Current Density – The current applied per cross-sectional area of the electrode
$R_{c,d}$ (Ω cm ²)*	$R_{c,d} = \pm \frac{(U_{ohm} + U_{act} + U_{con})}{i_{c,d}}$	Area-specific Resistance – The resistance of the cell due to the ohmic, activation and concentration polarization
$\frac{Q_t}{V}$ (mAh L ⁻¹)	$Q_t = nCF$	Theoretical Volumetric Capacity – The theoretical capacity that can be stored and extracted from a given volume of electrolyte
Capacity fade or Capacity decay (% cycle ⁻¹)	Slope of the capacity vs. number of cycles	Capacity fading – Capacity lost in percentage per operational cycle
E (Wh L ⁻¹)	$\frac{\int dQ_d dU_d}{V}$	Energy Density – Energy than can be extracted from a given volume of electrolyte
P (mW cm ⁻²)	Power (P) = V x i	Power Density – Power delivered per unit area
CE (%)	$CE = \frac{\int dQ_d}{\int dQ_c} \times 100$	Coulombic Efficiency – The ratio of discharge capacity to charge capacity
VE (%)	$VE = \frac{EE}{CE} \times 100$	Voltage Efficiency – The ratio of discharge voltage to charge voltage
EE (%)	$EE = \frac{\int dQ_d dU_d}{\int dQ_c dU_c} \times 100$	Energy Efficiency – The ratio of discharge energy to charge energy

* subscripts “c, d” denote charging and discharging processes

Figure 3. Pourbaix diagram of Zn in water. Reproduced with permission from Yu et al. [46].

classify developed RFB technologies (Figure 2). Additionally, this article aims to update recent advancements in the functionalization of organic molecules by reviewing various synthetic strategies for incorporating different functional groups. The overall purpose of this review is to examine Zn/Organic RFBs to understand if they can potentially achieve cost-competitiveness as long-duration BESS.

With this in mind, the article is organized into several sections (Figure 2). Section 2 provides an overview of the working principles of Zn/Organic RFBs emphasizing the role of the Zn-based negolytes. Section 3 explores different configurations of aqueous Zn/Organic RFBs, classified by posolyte type into i) TEMPO-based organics, ii) other organic compounds, and iii) organometallic-based catholytes. Sections 4 and 5 focus on non-aqueous Zn/Organic RFBs and biphasic membrane-free systems, respectively. Each section outlines and elaborates on the rationale behind investigating the specific type of Zn/Organic RFB – whether it is aqueous, non-aqueous, or membrane-free, as well as the main challenges associated with each battery configuration based on the chemistry of its anolyte and catholyte, respectively. To conclude, section 6 summarizes the key challenges of Zn/Organic RFBs and offers perspectives for future research.

2. Working principle and challenges of Zn/Organic RFBs

2.1. Key performance metrics of Zn/Organic RFBs

Conventional RFBs are discrete from solid-state batteries with the electrolytes being stored in two external tanks. That is, the energy density of the battery can ideally be increased linearly with the concentration of the electrolyte at the same power density. However, in a Zn/Organic hybrid RFB, the power and energy are not completely decoupled as the energy stored in the battery depends on both the area of the Zn anode and the concentration of the Zn negolyte. Although the energy density of the battery is the most distinguishing parameter among the various performance metrics used to evaluate RFBs, several other metrics also contribute to assessing their overall performance. Key metrics include the active species concentration, volumetric capacity, applied current density, flow rate, discharge voltage, and overpotentials at both electrodes, which form the foundation of RFB evaluation. All the performance metrics used to analyze Zn/Organic RFBs in this study have been summarized in Table 1.

The performance of Zn batteries; whether aqueous, non-aqueous, or polymer-based, primarily depends on the electrolyte, which enables zinc deposition and dissolution during electrochemical reactions.

2.2. Challenges of Zn-based aqueous electrolytes

The performance, reversibility, and safety of aqueous Zn batteries are profoundly influenced by the pH of the electrolyte, which governs Zn ion speciation, electrochemical window, and parasitic side reactions. Aqueous Zn systems typically operate under three pH regimes: acidic, neutral, and alkaline; each associated with distinct advantages and challenges. Understanding these differences is critical for optimizing Zn hybrid RFB design and extending cycle life. The electrochemical behaviors of Zn in these environments can be interpreted through the Pourbaix diagram (Figure 3) and corresponding Nernst equations.

2.2.1. Acidic electrolytes (pH 1 – 5)

In acidic electrolytes, zinc solubility is influenced by the concentration of Zn²⁺ ions. During electrodeposition, Zn undergoes a two-electron reduction reaction (Equation 1), with its potential determined by Equation 2.

$$E_{\text{Zn}^{2+}/\text{Zn}} = -0.763 + 0.0295 \log[\text{Zn}^{2+}] \text{ vs. SHE} \quad (2)$$

Key challenges in acidic electrolytes include: (i) Hydrogen evolution reaction (HER): High proton activity leads to significant hydrogen gas evolution, reducing coulombic efficiency (CE) and increasing safety risks due to gas pressure buildup [47]. Additionally, water depletion further lowers ionic conductivity and contributing to degradation [48]. (ii) Corrosion and dissolution: Zn corrosion and complexation by anions

Figure 4. Summary of the challenges faced by the Zn-based anolyte in Zn hybrid RFB.

result in continuous mass loss, self-discharge, and poor cycling stability [49],[50]. (iii) Incompatibility with cell components: Aggressive acidity can degrade metallic current collectors and seals, affecting long-term stability [51].

2.2.2. Neutral electrolytes (pH ~6–7)

Neutral Zn electrolytes offer a more balanced electrochemical environment. While Zinc deposition still follows Equation 1, hydrogen evolution is substantially reduced compared to acidic electrolytes due to the lower proton concentration.

Challenges in neutral electrolytes include: (i) Zincate formation: Partial hydrolysis of Zn^{2+} may lead to $Zn(OH)_4^{2-}$ formation, impairing deposition reversibility that can shorten the battery's cycle life [52]. (ii) Lower ionic conductivity: Compared to acidic and alkaline media, neutral electrolytes exhibit reduced ionic mobility, limiting charge transfer rates, and lowering power density. (iii) Dendrite formation: Surface inhomogeneities during cycling contribute to dendritic growth, which compromises safety and cycling life [53].

2.2.3. Alkaline electrolytes (pH 8–14)

Under alkaline conditions, hydroxide ions (OH^-) react with zinc ions to form zincate species $[Zn(OH)_4]^{2-}$. Therefore, these systems utilize the Zn/zincate redox couple (Equations 3 and 4):

$$E_{ZnO/Zn} = -0.439 - 0.0591pH \text{ vs. SHE} \quad (4)$$

Alkaline conditions enable more negative electrode potentials (-1.29 V vs. SHE), thus achieving higher theoretical energy density. However: (i) Zincate accumulation: Excess OH^- leads to $Zn(OH)_4^{2-}$ buildup, decreasing plating efficiency, potentially clogging porous electrodes, and potentially shortening the battery's cycle life [54]. (ii) Passivation: Over time, dense ZnO layers form, reducing active surface area and increasing internal resistance. (iii) Anisotropic dendrites: Alkaline pH promotes perpendicular dendritic Zn growth in a leaf-like structure, especially in concentrated electrolytes [55],[56],[57],[58].

The following Table gathers comparative overview of key challenges in aqueous Zn hybrid RFB as a function of the anolyte pH.

Comparative insights. While HER dominates in acidic media and dendrites are a shared issue across all pH regimes, their causes differ: in acidic systems, HER-related corrosion leads to rough deposits, while in

alkaline conditions, high OH^- concentration encourages perpendicular dendritic growth. Neutral systems exhibit moderate behavior in terms of both corrosion and dendrites but suffer from conductivity limitations. Understanding these mechanistic differences is essential for tailoring electrolytes to application-specific requirements.

2.3. Challenges of Zn-based non-aqueous electrolytes

Traditional aqueous Zn-based batteries have been widely researched and adopted, but they suffer from challenges such as HER, zinc corrosion, and dendrite formation (Figure 4). Non-aqueous Zn-based electrolytes offer an alternative solution by expanding the electrochemical stability window, minimizing side reactions, and improving the reversibility of zinc deposition and dissolution. Additionally, they simplify the electrodeposition process. However, these systems introduce their own set of challenges, necessitating optimized electrolyte compositions and electrode designs for practical application (Figure 4).

More specifically, challenges in non-aqueous electrolytes include: (i) Poor kinetics: In aqueous systems, Zn^{2+} ions exhibit high mobility due to strong solvation in water. In contrast, non-aqueous electrolytes provide weaker Zn^{2+} solvation, leading to low ionic conductivity, sluggish charge transfer, high overpotentials, and inefficient Zn deposition [59]. (ii) Zinc passivation: Zn can react with organic solvent molecules, forming an unstable solid-electrolyte interphase (SEI) or passivation layer, which increases electrode resistance and reduces Zn utilization [60]. (iii) Dendrite formation: Non-aqueous electrolytes often result in uneven Zn ion distribution and high local current densities, promoting dendrite growth [61]. These dendrites can pierce the separator, leading to short circuits and performance degradation. (iv) Cost and environmental impact: Many salts and solvents used in non-aqueous Zn electrolytes are expensive and pose environmental concerns, making large-scale adoption difficult (e.g., $(Zn(TFSI)_2)$, Thermo Fisher Scientific, 98%; costs US\$ 104 per g).

3. Aqueous Zn/Organic RFBs

Aqueous electrolytes are the most extensively studied due to their high ionic conductivity, relatively high active-material solubility, cost-effectiveness, and ease of handling [62],[63]. Commercial VRFBs typically rely on Nafion® membranes, which can account up to 30% of the total cell cost [64]. In contrast, aqueous Zn/Organic RFBs present a more

Figure 5. Structures and synthetic procedures of the reported TEMPO-based organic posolytes for aqueous Zn/Organic RFBs.

economical alternative by employing cost-effective ion-exchange and size-exclusion membranes [65],[66]. However, a key challenge in aqueous organic RFBs is capacity decay caused by the degradation of electro-active organic materials [67]. This issue is addressed through various synthetic modifications, resulting in more stable electrolytes. Additionally, beyond the conventional dual-flow RFB design, alternative cell configurations are proposed. A single-flow RFB was developed to simplify design by eliminating the need for a pump, making it ideal for applications with space or complexity constraints [65],[68]. Another innovative approach involved a three-compartment cell with three electrolytes and two membranes, designed to increase the operating voltage by utilizing an acidic electrolyte for one active species and an alkaline electrolyte for the other [69]. This section examines reported studies on different aqueous Zn/Organic RFBs, focusing on how the chemical nature of the organic-based posolytes influences performance. Table 3 summarized the key characteristics and performance metrics of these reported aqueous Zn/Organic RFBs, categorized by the type of the organic posolyte (TEMPO-based, Fe-based, and others).

3.1. TEMPO-based aqueous posolytes

Figure 5 summarizes various TEMPO-derivatives used as posolytes in aqueous Zn/Organic RFBs, highlighting their synthetic routes and redox potentials.

Orita et al. reported a hydroxyl group functionalized TEMPO (TEMPOL) which resulted in a solubility of up to 3.6 M in water [15]. It was hypothesized that TEMPOL mirrored the characteristics of TEMPO both chemically and electrochemically – disproportionation and influence of pH. The redox behaviour of TEMPOL was studied at various pHs with ideal CV at 0.61 V vs. Ag/AgCl observed at neutral and near neutral pH. At higher basic conditions, no reduction peak was observed as TEMPOL^+ was instantaneously converted back to TEMPOL. The performance trends in TEMPOL-based Zn/Organic RFBs demonstrate that both the membrane type (Nafion 212, SELEMION DSV) and the supporting electrolyte (NaCl, Na_2SO_4 , NaClO_4) significantly influence capacity retention and efficiency (Figure 6a). The Zn/TEMPOL RFB achieved its highest initial cycling efficiency at 10 mA cm^{-2} using Nafion 212 with NaClO_4 , retaining 51% capacity after 50 cycles. This was attributed to the higher solubility and lower basicity of NaClO_4 , which effectively suppressed TEMPOL precipitation. In contrast, NaCl led to precipitation, diminishing capacity. SELEMION DSV, being thicker and less conductive than Nafion 212, exhibited approximately twice the resistance and poorer performance. Furthermore, NaClO_4 appeared to oxidize the SELEMION membrane, further reducing efficiency. Two distinct discharge plateaus observed with Nafion 212 and NaClO_4 indicated a possible interaction between TEMPOL^+ and Nafion's SO_3^- groups, resulting in an unstable lower-voltage plateau that faded more rapidly – an effect absent with SELEMION and NaCl. UV-Vis and

Figure 6. a) Discharge capacities of Zn/TEMPO RFBs with various membrane and electrolyte combinations (adapted with permission of Elsevier from [15]). b) SEM images of a graphite felt anode after the charging process depicting different morphologies of the zinc deposits (reproduced with permission of ACS from [70]). c) Galvanostatic cycling profiles of various Zn/R-TEMPO flow batteries with 0.05 M posolyte at 10 mA cm⁻² for 300 cycles deposits (reproduced with permission of ACS from [74]). d) The reaction mechanism of MIACNH-TEMPO during the charge-discharge process, analyzed through in-situ Raman spectra, Raman spectra of, semi in-situ UV/Vis spectra, EPR spectra (reproduced with permission of Wiley from [75]). e) Galvanostatic cycling of 0.2 M DFTEMPO in 2 M NH₄Cl as posolyte and 0.4 M ZnCl₂ in 1.5 M NH₄Cl as negolyte, at 20 mA cm⁻² (reproduced with permission of RSC from [76]).

CV analyses showed TEMPOL concentration losses of ~51 – 58%, matching capacity decay and confirming degradation as the primary cause, with crossover being negligible. Furthermore, the overall capacity retained was enhanced when N₂ was bubbled through the electrolyte, indicating the effect of oxygen and dissolved gases. However, the capacity fade was still imminent. It was attributed to the disproportionation of TEMPOL which proportionally increased with its concentration. The use of other design combinations of membrane and supporting

electrolytes suffered from high cell resistances.

To further improve the chemical stability and solubility of TEMPOL, Winsberg et al. introduced an anionic substituent (SO₃⁻) into the TEMPO moiety (TEMPO-4-sulfate potassium salt, named as TEMPO-4-SPS in Figure 5) [70]. For this, TEMPOL was reacted with concentrated sulfuric acid at room temperature, showing no degradation due to the reversible disproportionation of TEMPO under these conditions. CV of the synthesized TEMPO-4-SPS in a 0.05 M ZnCl₂ and 0.05 M NH₄Cl electrolyte

revealed a redox potential of 0.61 V vs. Ag/AgCl with a peak split of 63 mV. Along with a high cell voltage of about 1.69 V, an energy density of 20 Wh L⁻¹ was obtained, which was on par with VRFBs. To suppress TEMPO precipitation in the charged state, higher concentrations of ZnCl₂ (2 M) and NH₄Cl (1 M) were used as supporting electrolytes, resulting in a lower cell resistance of 6.95 Ω cm². In comparison, an all-organic RFB with TEMPO exhibited a higher resistance of 9.62 Ω cm² at lower current density ranges [71]. Despite the high charge voltage cut-off limit (2.1 V), the formation of chlorine and hydrogen gases was not observed. Current densities of up to 80 mA cm⁻² were applied resulting in a relatively minimized capacity utilization (< 60%) [70]. A pumped RFB cell with 0.5 M posolyte operated at 40 mA cm⁻² demonstrated stable performance for 2.3 days, achieving a CE of 99.4% with no visible crossover of TEMPO-4-SPS into the anolyte. Notably, A reference cell utilizing 4-HO-TEMPO as cathode active material revealed significantly worse stability, which was ascribed to both crossover and self-oxidation. The Zn deposition on the felt cathode was also examined, revealing that the zinc deposit developed in agglomerates ranging from small angled granules attached on the graphite fibers to larger flat flakes growth around several fibers (Figure 6b). Long-term cycling in a non-pumped cell with a posolyte of smaller capacity (0.92 Ah L⁻¹) revealed a capacity retention of 93.6% after 1,100 cycles. Posolytes with higher concentrations (1 M) were also investigated but suffered from the precipitation of oxidized species. All the tests were performed at room temperature under ambient conditions, with no oxygen-induced side reactions of the active material, avoiding the need for inertization.

Building upon the focus on the stability of TEMPOL, Chang et al. reported a one-step cation-grafted TEMPO posolyte (named as g⁺-TEMPO in Figure 5) from TEMPOL to inhibit the side reactions experienced with TEMPOL and to further increase its solubility [72]. The electrochemical properties studied using the CV revealed diffusion and adsorption-controlled kinetics with the non-linearity of scan rate vs. the peak current. This suggests that enhancing electrode properties could improve performance, whereas increasing reactant concentration or optimizing electrolyte flow may have a lesser effect due to mass transport constraints. The grafted TEMPO exhibited smaller peak separation with higher peak currents, indicating faster kinetics and reduced polarization compared to its non-grafted counterpart. Compatible anion exchange membrane was synthesized with methylated poly-benzimidazole (PBI) to conduct Cl⁻ ions. A cross-linked meta-PBI membrane exchanged with Cl⁻ ions had a higher water uptake and a lower dry weight. A hybrid flow battery was set up with the 0.2 M g⁺-TEMPO posolyte and an equimolar ZnCl₂ and NH₄Cl negolyte with a 45 μm PBI membrane, graphite felt cathode and Zn plate anode. About 3 mm of spacing was kept between the membrane and the Zn anode to avoid the Zn deposit from damaging the membrane. Compared to TEMPOL, g⁺-TEMPO demonstrated improved coulombic efficiency (CE), enhanced reaction kinetics and cycling stability, with a capacity fade of 0.046% cycle⁻¹. The improved coulombic efficiency was attributed to the suppressed crossover of the positively charged g⁺-TEMPO through the anion exchange membrane. The cell exhibited a voltage efficiency (VE) of 90% with the resistance decreasing from 4 Ω to 1.9 Ω after long-term cycling and no gas evolution was observed. Moreover, both the energy efficiency (EE) and voltage efficiencies (VE) slightly increased over cycling, likely due to a decrease in cell resistance likely caused by progressive changes in the membrane's ionic channels, ion-exchange capacity, and the development of a rougher Zn surface during cycling. The Zn/TEMPOL hybrid RFBs exhibited certain capacity fading over cycling, which was more pronounced with the TEMPOL than with the g⁺-TEMPO posolyte. This capacity fading was primarily attributed to side reactions on the posolyte side, as no crossover was observed.

In another attempt to minimize the side reactions in TEMPO-based electrolytes, Chang et al. grafted TEMPO with an imidazolium-based substituent (named as Imidazolium-TEMPO in Figure 5) [73]. The imidazolium substitution on TEMPO offers several advantages over base

TEMPOL: (i) A positive redox potential shift of 0.15 V due to the electron-withdrawing nature of imidazolium, enhancing battery voltage output; (ii) Increased solubility, improving energy density (5.3 vs. 1.2 Ah L⁻¹ for TEMPOL); and (iii) Extended cycle life by reducing catholyte crossover. At a low current density of 1.25 mA cm⁻², the Zn/Organic RFB exhibited an average charge/discharge voltage of 1.67/1.64 V, while the CEs remained reasonable (95.9%). At higher currents, from 5 and 50 mA cm⁻², CEs improved to above 99.8%, surpassing those of unmodified TEMPOL. The galvanostatic cycling of the cell over 30 cycles exhibited an average CE, VE, and EE of 95.9%, 97.7% and 93.7%, respectively, with a capacity fade of 0.42% per cycle. An interesting pattern emerged in the galvanostatic profiles at 5 and 10 mA cm⁻², where a brief discharge slope appeared that was absent in previous cycles. However, this feature disappeared at a higher current density of 20 mA cm⁻². This suggests the possible involvement of an additional active component during discharge, potentially contributing to capacity fade. At even higher currents, the cell experienced significant voltage losses due to the membrane's low ion conductivity. Later, pre-processing of the membrane was adopted using 1 M HCl and 1 M NaCl, that helped to improve the VE. When the concentration of the posolyte was augmented to 0.4 M, the Zn/Organic RFB experienced a concentration polarization due to the poor ionic transport for the substituted TEMPO. Consequently, the capacity utilization greatly reduced from 45% at 1.25 mA cm⁻² to 12% at 5 mA cm⁻². Moreover, it was observed that the utilization ratio was dependent on the characteristics of the membrane as well. Hence, the membrane contributed to both the ohmic and concentration polarization resistances in this case. In this work, the authors did not exclusively discuss the issues related to the Zn anode.

To further elucidate the influence of electron donating and withdrawing functional groups on TEMPO, Fan et al. investigated different hydrophilic substituents (R = -OH, -NH₂, -COOH, -NHCOCH₃ on R-TEMPO to better understand their effect on the redox potential and the electrochemical stabilities [74]. Among the different substituents, 4-TEMPO-NHCOCH₃- (Figure 5) was seen to have the best redox reversibility with the highest peak current ratio and the lowest peak separation. The redox potentials and the kinetics of TEMPO derivatives were significantly impacted by the hydrophilic substitutions, with the amine-substituted TEMPO (named as TEMPO-NH₂ in Figure 5) having the highest redox potential and the fastest kinetics. For the flow battery tests, a Zn foil anode and graphite felt cathode with an anion exchange separator in a conventional flow setup were used. The Zn/R-TEMPO hybrid RFBs attained high OCVs in the range of 1.67 – 1.78 V. TEMPO-NH₂ experienced the highest capacity fade; with 50% retention and 4-TEMPO-NHCOCH₃ with the least; 99% retention, after 300 cycles (Figure 6c). The CVs of the negolyte at different cycling intervals revealed significant crossover for all the TEMPO-derivatives posolytes except 4-TEMPO-NHCOCH₃. Moreover, the decrease in UV-Vis absorbance corroborated the concentration loss. ESI-MS, EPR and NMR spectra of 4-TEMPO-NHCOCH₃ after the 1st and 100th cycle, showed that it was the least susceptible to disproportionation when compared to the other TEMPO derivatives under study. The radical energies calculated using DFT indicate that the stability of the NHCOCH₃ substituent is due to two key factors: first, it lowers the radical energy, enhancing the stability of the ring-opening bond; second, it provides significant spatial volume and steric hindrance, which helps prevent crossover reactions. The Zn/ 4-TEMPO-NHCOCH₃ RFB could achieve an energy density of 11.4 Wh L⁻¹ along with its exceptional stability (capacity retention > 99.65% day⁻¹). Similar to the previous work, the authors here did not comment on the issues related to the Zn anode.

Expanding on Chang's findings regarding imidazolium substitution, Fan et al. developed a novel posolyte active material by introducing a methylimidazole-substituted NH₂-TEMPO (named as MIACNH-TEMPO in Figure 5), achieving high solubility and a theoretical energy density of 105.4 Wh L⁻¹ [75]. Electrochemical characterization revealed a redox potential of 0.63 V vs. Ag/AgCl, a diffusion coefficient of 1.15 × 10⁻⁵ cm²/s, and a rate constant of 1.86 × 10⁻² cm/s, supporting

Figure 7. Structures of other organic molecules used as aqueous polyoxylates for Zn-Organic hybrid RFBs and the different cell configurations used in respective studies.

Figure 8. a) Cycling performance of the Zn/PANI RFB at 20 mA cm^{-2} , with an inset of the time vs. voltage profile (reproduced with permission of Elsevier from [65]). b) Schematic representation of a membrane-less Zn-quinone RFB (adapted with permission of Elsevier from [68]). c) Schematic of the double-membrane and three-electrolyte Zn/FQH₂ RFB (adapted with permission of Wiley from [69]). d) Short-time charge-discharge profiles of zinc plate, Zn mesh, Zn foam and Zn fibre anodes (reproduced with permission of MDPI from [78]).

high-performance battery operations with minimal voltage loss. Zn/MIAcNH-TEMPO hybrid RFB demonstrated exceptional cycling stability, with a capacity fade rate of 0.0005% per cycle over 1000 cycles, along with high coulombic (99.5% per day at 50 mA cm^{-2}) and energy efficiencies (70%). Comparative analyses showed that MIAcNH-TEMPO significantly outperformed AcNH-TEMPO, which exhibited faster capacity fade and more severe side reactions. A comprehensive relative stability of these negolytes by using in-situ Raman, UV-Vis, EPR, and ^1H NMR analyses, supported by DFT, confirmed the MIAcNH-TEMPO's stability, attributing it to electron density delocalization, reduced

Hirshfeld charge, and steric hindrance, which suppress crossover (Figure 6d). Raman and UV-Vis spectra detected stable N-O* radicals and +N=O species, indicating reversible redox behavior. EPR and ^1H NMR validated structural integrity after 1000 cycles. DFT further showed that π - π imidazolyl and p- π acetylamino substituents enhance electron delocalization, preventing side reactions like ring-opening and disproportionation, previously seen with the -NH₂ group. Building on the exceptional stability of 0.1 M MIAcNH-TEMPO, increasing its concentration to 1.5 M enhanced Zn anode utilization to 80 mAh cm^{-2} . Despite these demanding conditions, the Zn/Organic RFB maintained

90% capacity utilization, an energy density of 61.8 Wh L⁻¹, and stability over 400 hours. However, the authors speculated (without experimental evidence) that the slow kinetics of the Zn²⁺/Zn(s) pair could hinder performance, leading to potential inefficiencies and contribute to dendrite formation during cycling under practical conditions.

Yu et al. introduced an electron withdrawing functionalization group in TEMPO in the form of fluorine (named as DFTEMPO in Figure 5) to enhance the molecular stability, redox potential, and electrochemical performance of the RFB [76]. DFTEMPO had high water solubility (2.28 M in pure water) and stable crystalline structure, confirmed by XRD, where sodium ions bridged DFTEMPO molecules to enhance stability. EPR spectra confirmed the presence of radicals with unpaired electrons whilst ¹H, ¹⁹F and ¹³C NMR spectroscopies validated the intermediates and the target products of the synthesis. Electrochemical characterization showed a high oxidation potential (0.806 V vs. SHE), an electron transfer rate constant ($1.53 \times 10^{-2} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$), and a competitive diffusion coefficient ($2.74 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$), ensuring efficient charge transfer during operation. In battery tests, 0.2 M DFTEMPO posolyte demonstrated superior performance with a high OCV (1.64 V), peak power density (244.9 mW cm⁻²). Symmetric cell test of DFTEMPO revealed a minimal capacity decay in a of 0.022% h⁻¹ over 1000 cycles. However, the Zn/DFTEMPO hybrid RFB exhibited a capacity decay of 0.195% h⁻¹ (Figure 6e). The primary reason for capacity fade in the full RFB was crossover of the posolyte through the membrane, which accounted for approximately 85% of the capacity loss within 50 cycles. The permeability of DFTEMPO in its radical and oxoammonium forms was significantly higher than other modified TEMPO-based posolytes, leading to increased crossover and reduced cycle stability. Chemical degradation of redox-active materials contributed only 12% to the capacity loss, indicating that crossover was the dominant factor affecting capacity fade. The fluorine group improved chemical stability by lowering the electron density of the N–O radical, thereby suppressing side reactions. Additionally, DFT calculations revealed that the CF₂ functionality enhances molecular stability by increasing the oxidation potential and reducing susceptibility to molecular degradation pathways.

3.2. Other organic molecules as aqueous posolytes

Figure 7 summarizes various organic posolytes used in Zn-Organic RFBs, grouped by their respective cell configurations.

One of the earliest Zn-polymer hybrid RFB was proposed by Zhao et al., combining a suspension of polyaniline (PANI) catholyte with Zn anode [65]. PANI was chosen as the posolyte due to its redox properties, low cost, high conductivity, and environmental stability. The PANI microparticles were synthesized via two routes – chemical and electrochemical. The average particle size was approximately 12.5 μm for electrochemically synthesized PANI and about 14.1 μm for the chemical synthesized counterpart. The CV of chemically synthesized PANI in 2 M ZnCl₂ and 2 M NH₄Cl at pH 4.5 exhibited redox potential of 0.27 V vs. SCE. The electrochemically synthesized PANI exhibited two oxidation peaks, one at 0.22 V vs. SCE and another at 0.48 V vs. SCE, with the latter attributed to the oxidation of the aniline oligomer. The viscosities of the PANI suspension were found to be much higher when compared to the 2 M vanadium electrolyte (> 40 cP). A single flow design with a single pump and electrolyte reservoir was used to perform flow tests. During the battery operation, only the PANI suspension is pumped into the cathode compartment, where part of ZnCl₂ and NH₄Cl solution penetrates into the anode compartment via the microporous membrane. This polypropylene microporous membrane inhibited the crossover of PANI particles due to size exclusion. A capacity loss of 0.07% per cycle was observed during the galvanostatic charging and discharging of a Zn/PANI RFB at 20 mA cm⁻² (Figure 8a). This RFB could reach a maximum current density of 30 mA cm⁻² with relatively low average CE of 86%. Interestingly, in this work, the authors measured the IR drop using a reference cell. Despite being static, the IR-drop for zinc electrode was only 0.06 V (vs 0.31 V for PANI), indicating that the polarization at

the zinc anode is relatively low compared to the flowing PANI electrode. This suggests that the zinc anode may have a more stable performance under the tested conditions, but further details on stability parameters were not provided.

Leung et al. emphasized cell design innovation as opposed to posolyte molecular design by introducing a Zn/Organic hybrid RFB with a single flow and membrane-less configuration utilizing 1,4-benzoquinone (1,4-BQ), 1,2-benzoquinone (1,2-BQ) and 1,2-benzoquinone-3,5-disulfonic acid (1,2-BQDS) as organic posolytes (BQDS and pBQ in Figure 7) [77]. The cell voltages were higher than 1.45 V for all the Zn/quinone RFBs across a wide pH range (1 – 12). Although acidic electrolytes enabled higher cell voltages by positively shifting the redox potential of quinones, it promoted hydrogen evolution on the Zn anode. The membrane-free concept proposed by the authors relied on the slow dissolution rate of the electro-deposited Zn on the anode. The dissolution of electro-deposited Zn was analyzed by measuring the weight-loss of Zn anode. As expected, zinc dissolution rates were higher in acidic pH, reaching 25 mg h⁻¹ cm⁻², compared to <11.5 mg h⁻¹ cm⁻² at pH 7. All quinone molecules studied exhibited poor performance at 30 mA cm⁻², sustaining only twelve cycles. Moreover, the battery was charged only to an SOC of about 55%, which was calculated based on the theoretical capacities of the quinones. Even though the membrane-less system enabled the use of a higher current density (30 mA cm⁻²), the CEs for all the quinones were between 70 – 80%, further adding to the inferior capacity utilization. These low CE values were likely due to the severe self-discharge of the oxidized quinones in direct contact with the Zn anode (no membrane was used to avoid this cross-over).

Subsequently, Leung et al. continued to optimize the single-flow Zn/quinone hybrid using low-cost elements, Zn and 1,4-benzoquinone (pBQ) in a membrane-free configuration (Figure 8b) [68]. Like their previous study, the main challenge of this system is the self-discharge process caused by the dissolution of zinc in the presence of the oxidized active species. In fact, Zn/PANI hybrid RFB exhibited a decline in CEs from 75% to 69% over 20 cycles, which raises concerns about its long-term viability. They identify the influence of electrolyte flow on the stability of zinc electrodeposition, suggesting that fluctuations in performance are linked to this factor. Furthermore, the article emphasizes that optimizing Zn²⁺ concentrations can enhance transport efficiency, thereby reducing potential drop, improving CEs, and overall stability. The findings stress the need for further research into electrolyte compositions and operational parameters to mitigate the stability issues associated with zinc anodes, making it a critical area for future exploration in energy storage technologies. Another major drawback of the membrane-less system was its high polarization resistances leading to poor VEs, as they use a common electrolyte with both the electro-active species. Moreover, the average VE of 58.5% (charge and discharge voltages of ~1.51 V and ~0.92 V, respectively) attained by these RFBs were also on the lower side, yet claimed to be comparable to that of other membrane-free RFBs. This was due to the fact that the polarization was two-fold higher for the posolyte when compared to the negative, as Zn competed with pBQ and HQ for the reaction surface.

In a follow-up article, Tang et al. focused their study on optimizing various zinc anode architectures in combination with a hydroquinone/bezoquinone posolyte in membraneless Zn/Organic RFB [78]. 2D and 3D zinc anodes for hybrid-flow batteries were tested, addressing the challenges of dendrite formation and unclear mechanisms of zinc deposition in membraneless systems. XRD analysis showed smaller particle sizes and increased reactive sites in zinc mesh, foam, and fiber electrodes. SEM images revealed prominent porosity in zinc foam and fiber, with the latter exhibiting a 0.3 mm pore diameter and highwater affinity, enhancing zinc electrodeposition and dissolution. Porous zinc anodes had more negative OCVs, indicating energetically favorable reduction reactions, and lower charge-transfer resistances compared to zinc plates (Figure 8d). Multiphysics modeling highlighted improved active species distribution with porous zinc electrodes but slower electrolyte flows due to increased material resistance. The use of zinc fiber

Figure 9. Structures of all ferrocene-based aqueous polysolutes reviewed in this study and the different membranes used in their respective RFB studies.

anodes demonstrated an average CE of about 90% and VE of approximately 82% over 100 cycles at a current density of 30 mA cm^{-2} , indicating improved stability and performance. Additionally, the system demonstrated a lower capital cost of US\$ 136 per kWh, highlighting its economic feasibility.

The Aziz group employed an innovative three-compartment design to achieve elevated operating voltages in aqueous electrolytes by integrating electroactive species operating under both acidic and basic pH conditions within the same cell. (Figure 8c) [69]. Understandably, two membranes - Nafion 117 and SELEMION DSV were used to separate the negolyte and polysolite from the neutral electrolyte. The $\text{Zn}/[\text{Zn}(\text{OH})_4]^{2-}$ redox couple at pH 14.6 was used as the hybrid negolyte alongside 2,3,5,6-tetrakis(dimethylamino)methylhydroquinone (FQH_2) polysolite at pH -0.7. The cell exhibited a high voltage of 2 V at 50% SOC, benefited from the most negative and positive potentials of $\text{Zn}/[\text{Zn}(\text{OH})_4]^{2-}$ and FQH_2 , respectively, based on their potential-pH characteristics. However, some limitations before their usage were to be addressed. The quinone polysolite exhibited low reversibility and kinetics with a redox potential of 0.7 V vs. SHE with a peak separation of $> 500 \text{ mV}$. The kinetics and reversibility of FQH_2 were subsequently improved with the use of $\text{Ti}_4\text{O}_7/\text{Ketjenblack}$ (KB) electrocatalyst, reducing the peak separation to 35 mV. Moreover, quinones with high potential are susceptible to decomposition by Michael's attack. Hence, the C-H bonds were replaced with dimethylammonio substituents. The theoretical capacity of the assembled battery calculated based on the maximum concentration of FQH_2 (1.4 M) was 74 Ah L^{-1} . The RFB with $\text{Ti}_4\text{O}_7/\text{KB}$ electrocatalyst coated catholyte substrate exhibited superior rate capability and voltage efficiency, maintaining higher discharge capacities and lower overpotentials across all current densities compared to catalyst-free cells. Moreover, the cell showed stable performance for 50 cycles when cycled at 20 mA cm^{-2} with a capacity retention of 99.92% per cycle without the electrocatalyst. Authors have identified three primary degradation mechanisms of the Zn/Organic RFB: pH leakage, zincate ion crossover, and decomposition of FQH_2 (mentioned earlier). The pH of the neutral electrolyte decreased during cycling, indicating a proton leakage across

the SELEMION DSV membrane. Therefore, the choice of electrolytes, such as the use of NaOH and NaCl, plays a significant role in maintaining stable cycling behavior and overall performance of the zinc anode. Moreover, the zincate ion crossover through the Nafion 117 membrane can affect performance and stability, leading to capacity fade over time. Therefore, advances in membrane perm-selectivity were pointed out as essential for addressing the challenges related to zinc anode stability, as they can minimize ion crossover and enhance overall battery performance.

3.3. Organometallic aqueous polysolites

Figure 9 summarizes ferrocene-based organometallic polysolites used in Zn/Organic RFBs, highlighting the employed membranes.

Xie et al. reported an iron-ligand complex ($\text{Fe}(\text{bpy})_3\text{Cl}_2$) in near-neutral pH polysolite as an environmentally friendly choice for Zn/organometallic hybrid RFB [79]. The CV of the complex exhibits a redox potential of 0.79 V vs. SCE in a 2 M NaCl aqueous electrolyte with a peak separation of 60 mV. It showed faster kinetics than FeCl_2 in 2 M aqueous NH_4Cl , which had a peak difference of 80 mV. The hybrid RFB was tested in a conventional setup with two types of membranes – microporous Celgard 3501 and ion-selective Nafion 115 membrane. With the microporous membrane, the crossover of oxidized complex ($\text{Fe}(\text{bpy})_3^{3+}$) to the negolyte side of the battery was observed. This led to the self-discharge side reaction of the oxidized complex and the Zn foil anode, reducing it to $\text{Fe}(\text{bpy})_3^{2+}$ which eventually moved back to the polysolite side. This phenomenon was confirmed through the change in the colour of the negolyte. Hence, the charging process lasted for more than 20 h which was ~ 8 times more than the theoretical charging time and still failed to reach the charging cut-off. Nafion 115 had better selectivity and the negolyte remaining colourless over 300 cycles whereas the membrane exposed to the polysolite side turned red after 20 cycles. When the Zn/ $\text{Fe}(\text{bpy})_3\text{Cl}_2$ RFB was cycled galvanostatically at 1 mA cm^{-2} , a capacity retention of 80% was observed after 200 cycles. The capacity fade was attributed to the containment of the complex in

Figure 10. a) CVs of 10 mM Fc-SO₃Na and 10 mM BrFc-SO₃Na in 1 M Li₂SO₄ at 100 mV s⁻¹ and b) Capacity vs. voltage profiles non-targeted and targeted RFB (reproduced with permission of Elsevier from [80]). c) CE, VE and EE of Zn/Fc-SO₃NH₄ RFB with 0.5 M NaCl + 0.5 M NH₄Cl as the supporting electrolyte. (adapted with the permission of ACS [82]).

the membrane channels due to its large size. Furthermore, from the EIS measurements, it was derived that the increase in impedance could be predominantly attributed to the membrane.

Yu et al. reported a synthesized anionic sulfonated ferrocene derivative (Fc-SO₃Na in Figure 9) with a solubility of 2.5 M (67 Ah L⁻¹) as a polysolite active-material in a pH-neutral aqueous Zn/Organic RFB [80]. A three-step synthesis process utilizing ferrocene and 3-bromopropionyl chloride as primary starting materials was carried out, potentially questioning the commercialization. The electrochemical properties studied using cyclic voltammetry and linear sweep voltammetry revealed excellent stability and reversibility in both neutral (0.5 M Na₂SO₄) and acidic (1 M H₂SO₄) solutions. The diffusion coefficient and electron transfer rate constant of Fc-SO₃Na in 0.5 M Na₂SO₄ were 3.17 × 10⁻⁶ cm² s⁻¹ and 1.06 × 10⁻² cm s⁻¹, which were moderately higher when compared to other common polysolite active-materials. In contrast, the molecule exhibited instability in alkaline media, characterized by a gradual decrease in peak currents and the formation of a precipitate on the working electrode. In a full RFB setup with a Zn anode, Fc-SO₃Na demonstrated excellent cycling stability with 99.9975% capacity retention per cycle at a polysolite concentration of 21 mM in pH-neutral

solution. At higher polysolite concentration (1.5 M), the cell achieved a volumetric capacity of 23 Ah L⁻¹ and an energy density of 27.1 Wh L⁻¹. The cell had negligible capacity fade after 60 cycles at 80 mA cm⁻², indicating the superior stability of Fc-SO₃Na even at higher concentration. However, the formation of dendrites on the Zn anode led to premature cell failure. To enhance capacity further, researchers employed a redox-targeting strategy, utilizing LiFePO₄ as a solid booster in the polysolite tank, along with BrFc-SO₃Na and Fc-SO₃Na as redox mediators (Figure 10 a,b). To evaluate the performance of a redox targeting-based flow battery, a catholyte containing 21 mM Fc-SO₃Na and 15.8 mM BrFc-SO₃Na in 1 M Li₂SO₄ solution was utilized, with a Zn plate serving as the anode. Following the first cycle, 400 mg of LiFePO₄ flakes (64.0 mAh) was introduced into the cathodic tank, significantly enhancing cell capacity. The observed capacity increase (57.4 mAh) corresponded to 89.6% of the theoretical capacity of LiFePO₄, at a current density of 2.5 mA cm⁻². This high material utilization was also evident at elevated current densities (5.25 mA cm⁻²), although the actual volumetric capacity was slightly lower due to excess electrolyte in the tubing and cell.

Expanding on the favorable solubility and electrochemical properties observed in ferrocene derivatives, Kim et al. developed a

dimethylethylferrocenylmethylammonium bromide (named as Fc1N112-Br in Figure 9) posolyte via a simple single-step synthesis [81]. Fc1N112-Br exhibited a maximum solubility of 2.9 M in an aqueous solution at room temperature without any supporting electrolytes. The redox potentials of Fc1N112-Br at different concentrations ranged from 0.418 to 0.467 V, with the peaks showing a slight rightward shift as the concentration increased. The anodic and cathodic diffusion coefficients for 0.5, 1.0, and 1.5 M Fc1N112-Br electrolytes ranged from 1.821 to $2.570 \times 10^{-8} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, showing no significant variation with increasing concentration, which indicates electrochemical stability and reversibility. Charge transfer coefficients were close to 0.5, indicating quasi-reversible behavior and symmetric energy barriers for oxidation and reduction. Kinetic constants ranged from 1.205×10^{-7} to $4.674 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$, suggesting an inverse relationship between kinetic constant and viscosity. A full Zn/Organic RFB with 0.2 M Fc1N112-Br posolyte demonstrated an average discharge capacity retention ratio of 99.9% and coulombic efficiency of 95.7% over 20 cycles when cycled with current density of 5 mA cm^{-2} .

Yao et al. directed their efforts toward the stability of the active material by introducing a sulfate-modified ferrocene (named as Fc-SO₃NH₄ in Figure 9), highlighting the role of supporting electrolytes in stability and performance [82]. The solubilities of Fc-SO₃NH₄ in water, 2 M NaCl and 2 M NH₄Cl were 0.41 M, 0.18 M, and 0.11 M. The cyclic voltammograms of Fc-SO₃NH₄ in 1 M NaCl and 1 M NH₄Cl were almost similar, with a half-cell potential of 0.38 V. In both supporting salts, the peak separation was almost unchanged with diffusion-controlled kinetics and identical diffusion coefficients. The flow battery tests were conducted in a conventional setup with graphite felt cathode, Zn metal anode, and a Nafion 212 membrane with a current density of 20 mA cm^{-2} for all the tests. Electrolytes with 2 M NaCl supporting electrolyte showed nearly 50% capacity degradation after 100 cycles compared to the ones with 2 M NH₄Cl which had a capacity retention of 94% between the 20th and the 85th cycle. This was attributed to the greater stability of ammonium salts compared to sodium salts. Additionally, electrolytes with NH₄Cl as the supporting salt exhibited higher conductivity than those with NaCl. For this reason, both the VE and EE were also relatively higher in NH₄Cl electrolyte. In addition, reducing electrolyte concentration prolonged the battery lifetime. For example, a Zn/ Fc-SO₃NH₄ RFB that used a combination of supporting salts (0.5 M NaCl + 0.5 M NH₄Cl) showed a capacity retention as high as 92.55% after 100 consecutive charge/discharge cycles (Figure 10 c), showing high efficiencies. Though authors used ZnBr₂ anolyte, they did not comment on related corrosivity, toxicity, self-discharge, Br₂ crossover, among others, which indirectly relates to the stability of the zinc anode.

Fernandez-Benito et al. reported a novel highly water dispersed amphiphilic diblock copolymer nanoparticles containing redox-active ferrocene units (named as P1Fc in Figure 9). Using nanoparticle suspensions aims to address the limitations of existing Zn/organic hybrid RFBs, which include the high cost of membranes, the low solubility of organic redox-active materials in water, and their low capacity [83]. These nanoparticles were synthesized via reversible addition-fragmentation chain transfer (RAFT) polymerization, utilizing acrylic acid and 4-vinylbenzyl chloride as the hydrophilic and hydrophobic blocks, respectively. Dimethyl aminomethyl ferrocene was incorporated into the hydrophobic block to provide redox activity, achieving a concentration of $1.7 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mmol per mg}$ of polymer. FT-IR, UV-Vis, ¹H NMR successfully confirmed the synthesis and properties of the ferrocene-containing amphiphilic block copolymer nanoparticles. DLS measurements showed that the incorporation of ferrocene might influence the self-assembly behavior and aggregation tendencies of the block copolymer nanoparticles in aqueous solutions. Cryo-EM analysis provided visual confirmation of the nanoparticle formation and revealed smaller sizes compared to DLS measurements, potentially due to differences in sample preparation and measurement conditions. STEM imaging further supported the nanoparticle formation and highlighted potential differences in aggregation behavior between different block

copolymer compositions. The nanoparticles exhibited excellent water dispersibility up to 6 g L^{-1} , resulting in a theoretical capacity of 4.78 mAh at 10.5 mM Fc. Electrochemical analysis revealed efficient charge transport between the ferrocene centers within the nanoparticles, with a diffusion coefficient of $3.3 \times 10^{-11} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and a rate constant of $6.8 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$. When evaluated as a poly-posolyte material in a Zinc/Organic hybrid RFB using a cheap dialysis membrane, the dispersed copolymer nanoparticles achieved a peak capacity of 3.1 mAh with no evidence of crossover. However, capacity fading was observed, primarily due to nanoparticle aggregation and sedimentation, along with retention inside the graphite felt electrode over time. The findings highlighted the potential of ferrocene-containing polymer nanoparticles as an attractive active-material for high-capacity AORFBs, but further optimization is needed to address capacity fading and improve long-term cycling stability.

To evaluate the impact of temperature on ferrocene-co-polymer stability, Ivan et al. investigated the *in situ* thermal stability of a ferrocene-based FPMAM-co-METAC co-polymer (named as PFc in Figure 9) posolyte in a Zinc/Organic hybrid RFB with a size-exclusion membrane, emphasizing the role of heating setups and PFc degradation mechanisms [66]. The ferrocene mole fraction was determined to be 16% (27 mM PFc, 0.1 M ZnCl₂, 0.8 M NH₄Cl posolyte), consistent with cerimetric titration and atomic absorption spectroscopy, confirming full material capacity utilization. The electrolyte demonstrated self-charging when exposed to air, especially at elevated temperatures, making it essential to conduct tests in an argon-filled glovebox. Zn/Organic RFB demonstrated a high voltage of 1.24 V, coulombic and energy efficiencies of 99.3% and 90.0%, respectively, and a capacity fade rate of $0.2\% \text{ d}^{-1}$ (after 14 days) at ambient temperatures (28°C) in a glovebox. Although UV-Vis and CV of electrolytes ruled out PFc polymer crossover through the dialysis membrane, ESI-MS detected TMA-EtOH in the negolyte, which is a degradation product formed by hydrolysis of the PFc. Full RFB tests showed higher capacity fade compared to symmetric PFc/PFc cells. This is because, in the Zn/Organic full RFB, the crossover of degradation products is more detrimental: once is formed, the decomposition product leaves the posolyte, thus, shifting the reaction equilibrium toward further decomposition. The thermal stability was assessed with four heating setups commonly used in the literature. Results showed that only the thermostat-based setup, which heats the entire RFB system, accurately and uniformly maintained the target temperature of 60 °C. Using the optimized thermostat setup, the capacity fade rate was measured remaining stable at $0.2\% \text{ d}^{-1}$ up to 38°C, increased to $0.3\% \text{ d}^{-1}$ at 50°C, and escalated rapidly at 60 °C, indicating a new decomposition mechanism. Unbalanced, compositionally symmetric flow cell cycling and ex-situ SOC analysis revealed that accelerated capacity fade at 60 °C was due to an intrinsic decomposition of the ferrocene complex with the following reduction of the PFc electrolyte. The study revealed the important role of crossover of degradation products on accelerating the capacity fading of Zn/Organic RFB, and highlights the importance of establishing proper, reproducible thermal stability assessment experiments to unravel decomposition mechanisms, discover new approaches to modify the existing redox-active molecules, and identify new capacity fade suppression/recovery approaches.

4. Non-aqueous Zn/Organic RFBs

While aqueous Zn/Organic RFBs have demonstrated significant progress in terms of conductivity and cost, they remain limited by issues such as hydrogen evolution and restricted cell voltage, which ultimately limits the energy density achievable in these systems. To overcome these limitations, some researchers are exploring non-aqueous electrolyte systems, which offer a transformative approach to enhancing RFB performance. By extending the electrochemical stability window beyond 2 V, non-aqueous electrolytes significantly improve energy density, making them well-suited for high-performance applications. Moreover, several non-aqueous solvents, such as acetonitrile and carbonate-based

Figure 11. (a) Schematic representation of the copolymer structures: P(TEMPO-co-PEGMA) (P1 and P2) in different molar ratios and P(TEMPO-co-METAC) (P3). (b) Cyclic voltammogram of 0.1 M Zn(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O (dashed line) and 0.01 M P1 (solid line) in EC/DMC/DEC (v:v:v, 1:1:1), scan rate 50 mV s⁻¹. (c) Long-term cycling of a static non-aqueous Zn/poly(TEMPO) hybrid RFB with constant current of 1.4 mA cm⁻². (Adapted with permission of Wiley from [26]).

systems, exhibit excellent thermal and electrochemical stability, addressing concerns related to freezing, evaporation associated with water, and solvent degradation (for instance, water electrolysis). Recent advancements in non-aqueous RFBs have also demonstrated improved ion-selectivity and enhanced redox kinetics, paving the way for more compact, long-lasting, and efficient energy storage solutions. These innovations could play a crucial role in grid stabilization, renewable energy integration, and next-generation portable power systems.

Table 4 summarized the key characteristics and performance metrics of the reported non-aqueous Zn/Organic RFBs. In one of the first examples of using non-aqueous solvents in Zn/Organic RFBs, Winsberg et al. introduced the Zn/poly(TEMPO) hybrid RFB as a green, safe, and efficient energy storage system, emphasizing the advantages of the Zn anode and the interaction of various TEMPO-containing polymers with the Zn anode [26]. The study examines several polymers, including P(TEMPO-co-PEGMA) with different molar ratios (P1 and P2) and P(TEMPO-co-METAC) (P3), each tailored for specific solvent environments (Figure 11a). In the non-aqueous Zn/Organic RFB, polymer P1 is dissolved in a solvent mixture comprising ethylene carbonate, dimethyl carbonate, and diethyl carbonate in a 1:1:1 ratio (v/v), achieving a theoretical energy density of 8.1 Wh L⁻¹. In contrast, the aqueous Zn/Organic RFB employs P2 and P3, containing supporting salts including 1.0 M ZnCl₂, 1.0 M NH₄Cl for P2 and 0.71 M NaCl, 0.08 M ZnCl₂, 0.08 M NH₄Cl for P3. These salts enhance ionic conductivity and inhibit undesired reactions, such as zinc hydroxide formation. The zinc anode is pivotal in achieving a stable potential window of up to 2 V in aqueous media. This stability is attributed to the high overpotential for hydrogen evolution, which prevents water electrolysis at high voltages. During the charging process, Zn²⁺ are reduced and deposited as metallic zinc (Zn⁰) on the anode surface, forming a solid layer. While the zinc

deposition process is robust, dendrite formation during prolonged cycling poses challenges. These issues are mitigated by modifying the anode half-cell to include additional space and by using carbon paper to enhance the electrode surface area.

In aqueous electrolytes, Zn²⁺/Zn⁰ couple demonstrates improved behavior compared to non-aqueous electrolytes, with reduced peak separation in CV, enabling higher current densities of up to 20 mA cm⁻². These configurations also exhibit stable discharge capacities and long-term cycling performance, retaining 78.6% of the initial capacity after 1000 cycles. CE remains consistently high (>90%), and EE exceeds 80%, with no evidence of capacity decay, water electrolysis, or gas evolution during operation. In non-aqueous electrolytes, the Zn anode maintains effective redox behavior but faces kinetic limitations due to the low ionic conductivity of carbonate-based solutions (Figure 11b). This results in lower applicable current densities, up to 4 mA cm⁻², and a potential drop between the charging and discharging plateaus. Additionally, the aqueous Zn/Organic RFB achieved higher OCVs (1.7 V) compared to non-aqueous counterpart (1.3 V). Despite these challenges, continuous cycling of a static nonpumped battery with steady current of 1.4 mA cm⁻² revealed very slow capacity decay of only 0.04% per cycle and high coulombic efficiencies (>99.7%) (Figure 11 c). Moreover, the non-aqueous RFB still attains higher theoretical energy densities than aqueous counterparts, 8.1 Wh L⁻¹ vs. 4.1 Wh L⁻¹, due to the high solubility of P1 in organic carbonates.

In their next study, Winsberg et al. developed block copolymer micelles with a TEMPO corona as the cathode active material [84]. The micelles are formed by the self-assembly of the block copolymer PTMA-b-PS in an organic electrolyte composed of ethylene carbonate, dimethyl carbonate, and diethyl carbonate in a 1:1:1 (v/v) ratio, containing 0.5 M Zn(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O as the supporting electrolyte. The

Figure 12. (a) Cyclic voltammograms of two-electron transfer redox of P1–P3 at 10 mV s^{-1} . (b) Redox pathway of P3 two-electron transfer. (c) a) Voltage and power density dependencies on discharge current density. (d) Cycling stability and Coulombic efficiency of the RFB with 0.6 M P3 in a mixed solvent (DMF/H₂O = 1:5, volume ratio) at a current density of 40 mA cm^{-2} . (Adapted with permission of ACS from [85]).

micellar solution contains PTMA-b-PS at a concentration of 13 mg mL^{-1} , which represents its maximum solubility. The micelles consist of a polar TEMPO-methacrylate core and a nonpolar styrene corona, with a well-defined size that plays a critical role in the RFB performance. Dynamic light scattering measurements revealed that the micelles have an apparent hydrodynamic radius of $\sim 40 \text{ nm}$ in their charged state, with secondary aggregates having a radius of about 310 nm . Transmission electron microscopy confirmed these findings, showing individual micelles with diameters ranging from 50 to 75 nm in the charged state and larger aggregates. These micellar structures maintain their integrity during charge-discharge cycles, ensuring molecular stability and efficient redox activity. Enhanced solubility in the charged state further improves the performance, preventing precipitation or aggregation that could degrade battery efficiency.

The system demonstrated excellent electrochemical performance, including a diffusion coefficient of $1.8 \times 10^{-7} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, indicating efficient charge transport. The non-aqueous Zn/Organic battery, which was assembled with a dialysis membrane, achieved stable cycling performance across current densities from 0.2 to 3 mA cm^{-2} , with long-term tests at 1.5 mA cm^{-2} showing 95% retention of the initial discharge capacity over 1000 cycles. The Zn anode complements the micellar polysolite by offering high chemical stability and avoiding self-discharge or oxygen-related side reactions, even under ambient conditions. This combination of micellar polysolite and Zn anode demonstrates a synergistic effect, enhancing the overall stability, efficiency, and scalability.

Later, Wang et al. focused on developing a new type of polysolite for Zn/Organic aqueous RFBs by engineering para-substituted triphenylamine (TPA) derivatives [85]. The study demonstrated that 4,4',4''-trihydroxytriphenylamine (P3), derived from TPA, exhibited a reversible $2e^-$ transfer system through an enol/keto redox mechanism, which is highly beneficial for stable and efficient energy storage (Figure 12b). This conversion improved the electrochemical behavior of TPA, enabling it to have a high kinetic rate constant of $1.1 \times 10^{-1} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$, making it superior to previous organic redox couples used in RFBs. The performance of the P3-based system was evaluated in an aqueous RFB setup paired with a Zn anode. The resulting battery achieved a working voltage of 1.4 V , a capacity of 22.5 Ah L^{-1} and an energy density of 16 Wh L^{-1} when using a DMF/H₂O (1:5, v/v) mixed solvent. Notably, the system showed satisfactory cycling stability, retaining 80% of its capacity after 300 cycles at a current density of 40 mA cm^{-2} , indicating a promising long-term performance. The study highlighted that molecular engineering can effectively transform organic molecules with poor stability into highly reversible and efficient ones, paving the way for safer, cost-effective, and high-capacity organic aqueous RFBs. This approach also demonstrated energy densities close to those of VRFBs, with a peak power density of 230 mW cm^{-2} , showcasing the potential for scalable applications in grid energy storage. The study also highlighted the potential for intermittent cycling, revealing that the battery maintained good capacity retention and minimal voltage decay during periods of rest, which is critical for real-world energy storage applications.

Figure 13. (a) Redox reaction of TEMPOL posolyte and Zn negolyte during charge-discharge process. (b) Cyclic voltammograms of Zn(OH)_4^{2-} and TEMPOL (4HT in the legend) at 20 mV s^{-1} scan rate. (c) Efficiency plot of CE, VE, and EE over 100 cycles. (d) Capacity retention and volumetric capacity. (Adapted with permission from IOP publishing [86]).

Further, Deshmukh et al. developed a hybrid aqueous alkaline Zn/TEMPOL system combining $\text{Zn(OH)}_4^{2-}/\text{Zn}$ redox couple with the organic free radical posolyte TEMPOL to achieve a cell voltage of 2.1 V, surpassing conventional neutral Zn/TEMPO systems [86]. Zn(OH)_4^{2-} , a soluble complex that facilitates efficient charge transfer and diffusion. This high voltage, coupled with a demonstrated energy density of 25.32 Wh L^{-1} , represents a notable improvement, addressing the typical limitations of low cell voltage and energy density. The alkaline conditions stabilize the zinc redox couple, minimizes hydrogen evolution and allows efficient cycling with a remarkable capacity retention of 99.99% over 100 cycles (Figure 13d). TEMPOL exhibits a redox potential of 0.63 V vs. Ag/AgCl, excellent solubility, and robust structural stability. Its electrochemical performance was enhanced by dissolving it in a mixed solvent system with LiPF₆ and additives like ethylene carbonate and dichloroethane to improve ionic conductivity. CV revealed reversible redox peaks for both the negolyte and posolyte, confirming their suitability for efficient charge transfer. The TEMPOL posolyte displayed diffusion coefficients of $1.08 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (oxidation) and $1.26 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (reduction), indicative of rapid electron exchange and robust kinetics. Galvanostatic charge-discharge tests conducted across current densities of 5 to 40 mA cm^{-2} highlighted stable performance with CE of 90%, VE up to 85%, and EE of 60% at 40 mA cm^{-2} . The long-term stability and high CE were attributed to the minimal degradation of the TEMPOL posolyte and efficient zinc deposition. Post-cycling analyses, including SEM and Raman spectroscopy, confirmed uniform zinc deposition and minimal morphological changes in the electrodes.

5. Membrane-free Zn-Organic RFBs

Membrane-free RFBs that use immiscible electrolytes offer a fundamentally different approach aimed at reducing cost and complexity of conventional RFB by eliminating the problematic ion-selective membrane. This architecture tackles some of the persistent issues encountered in both aqueous and non-aqueous RFBs, including high membrane cost and the limited performance of membranes in terms of high ohmic resistance and imperfect separation of active species. The concept of membrane-free redox flow batteries based on immiscible or liquid-liquid biphasic electrolytes was first introduced by Marcilla et al. in 2017 [87]. Unlike conventional RFBs, where the active species are dissolved in electrolytes separated by an expensive ion-exchange membrane, this design relies solely on thermodynamic principles to keep the two electrolytes separated. However, a major drawback of this approach is the self-discharge reaction that occurs when the dissolved “charged” active species come into contact at the liquid-liquid interface. This leads to spontaneous recombination of the species, coming back to their respective uncharged states and resulting in low coulombic efficiencies [88]. To overcome this challenge, a hybrid membrane-free configuration employing a zinc anode and an organic-based posolyte has been recently proposed (Figure 14a). In this configuration, the “charged” species in the negolyte are not dissolved in the electrolyte but instead exist as metallic zinc (Zn), remaining as a solid deposited on the current collector. This prevents direct contact between the “charged” species at the interphase, drastically minimizing unwanted self-discharge reactions. Indeed, the use of a zinc foil as the negative electrode, in combination with an immiscible posolyte, has become one of the most

Figure 14. a) Schematic representation of Membrane-free Zn/Organic redox flow battery. b) Schematic illustration of the Self-stratified Battery based on TEMPO-Zn with stirring and c) Cycling performance of cell (reproduced with permission of CellPress from [90]). d) Schematic Operando UV-visible spectroscopy and e) Operando UV-visible spectra of 1 mM C3-PTZ in battery at various cycle numbers at charged states (reproduced with permission of ACS from [91]). f) Charge/discharge profiles of Zn/PTZ batteries at the 5th cycle (reproduced with permission of Elsevier from [92]). g) Charge-discharge curves (at 2.5 mA cm⁻²) were obtained in static and under flow conditions (20 mL min⁻¹). Photographs of the reactor with the colored polysolite at different states of charge SOC (reproduced with permission of Elsevier from [93]).

Figure 15. Overview of key strategies and challenges in Zn/Organic RFBs across different system configurations.

Table 2

Comparative analysis of Zn-based aqueous electrolytes.

Property	Acidic (pH 1–5)	Neutral (pH ~6–7)	Alkaline (pH 8–14)
Zn Speciation	Zn ²⁺ (aq)	Zn ²⁺ /Zn(OH) ₂ ²⁻ (equilibrium)	[Zn(OH) ₄] ²⁻ (dominant)
Anode Reaction	Zn ²⁺ (aq) + 2e ⁻ ↔ Zn (s)	Zn ²⁺ (aq) + 2e ⁻ ↔ Zn (s)	Zn(OH) ₂ + 2H ⁺ + 2e ⁻ ↔ Zn + 2H ₂ O
Redox Potential (vs. SHE)	-0.76 V	-0.76 V	-1.29 V
HER Tendency	High	Moderate	Low
Corrosion Risk	Severe	Moderate	Moderate
Dendrite Formation	Moderate	Moderate-to-High	High
Conductivity	High	Low-to-Moderate	High
Zincate Formation	Not significant	Moderate	Significant
Component Compatibility	Low	High	Moderate
Cycle life	Short	Moderate	Moderate-to-Long

widely adopted strategies for developing membrane-free RFBs with high coulombic efficiencies and practical state of charge (SOC). In the following sections, we review the reported studies based on the nature of the immiscible electrolytes used in these innovative membrane-free Zn/Organic batteries. Table 5 summarized the key characteristics and performance metrics of these reported membrane-free Zn/Organic RFBs.

5.1. Aqueous- Non-aqueous immiscible electrolytes

Gong et al. presented in 2017 the first example of such a system using a zinc metal electrode in an aqueous negolyte paired with an immiscible non-aqueous posolyte [89]. The posolyte consisted of a mixture of butylacetate and an ionic liquid having ferrocene dissolved as active species. The battery was tested over 20 cycles at 0.1 mA cm⁻² in a static configuration, but it demonstrated poor performance. Coulombic efficiency was low (78%), and capacity utilization was extremely limited, reaching only 1%. These issues were likely due to the crossover of ferrocenium species and the very high ohmic resistance of the cell, which was measured at 810 Ω cm⁻².

Significant improvement in the performance was demonstrated by Meng et al. using a biphasic electrolyte system generated through a salting-out effect, achieved by mixing TEGDME, MgSO₄, LiTFSI, and ZnSO₄ [90]. In this system, the resulting aqueous phase was used as negolyte merging a Zn plate while the non-aqueous phase served as posolyte dissolving a high concentration of TEMPO (1.5 M), leading to a theoretical energy density of 20 Wh L⁻¹ (Figure 14b). The membrane-free Zn/Organic battery exhibited an OCV of 1.45 V and demonstrated remarkable stability, showing no capacity fading over more than two months of cycling (150 cycles) at 4 mA cm⁻² (0.2C) (Figure 14c). Moreover, it maintained high efficiencies with coulombic efficiency of 99%, voltage efficiency of 92% and energy efficiency of 92%. Although the battery was operated in a static configuration, stirring the posolyte improved capacity utilization from 55% (without

Table 3
Summary of the characteristics and performance of published Aqueous Zn/Organic RFBs.

RFB	Active Species & concentration	Supporting electrolyte (Negolyte//Posolyte)	Electrode +/-	OCV (V)	Cycles/ current density (mA cm ⁻²)	CE/VE/EE (%)	Q _t ^a (Ah L ⁻¹)	Q _p ^a (Ah L ⁻¹)	Q _i /Q _f ^a (%)	E ^b (Wh L ⁻¹)	Membrane/ Flow Rate	Ref
TEMPO-based	Zn/1 M TEMPOL	1 M Zn(CH ₃ CO ₂) ₂ , 1 M NaCl//3M NaClO ₄	Graphite felt/ Zn foil	1.65	100/10	90/78/70	26.8	1.1	■	5	Nafion 212/ 20 mL min ⁻¹	[15]
	Zn/0.6 M TEMPOL-4-SPS	2 M ZnCl ₂ , 2 M NH ₄ Cl//2 M ZnCl ₂ , 2 M NH ₄ Cl	Graphite felt/ Zn Foil	1.69	50 (2.3 days)/40	99/70/69	16.1	8	■	■	Fumasep F-930-RFD/ 20 mL min ⁻¹	[70]
	Zn/0.2 M g+-TEMPO	0.3 M ZnCl ₂ , 0.3 M NH ₄ Cl//1 M NaCl	Graphite felt/ Zn Plate	1.65	140/20	99/72/72	5.36	1.85	94	9.25	Polybenzimidazole (PBI)/55 mL min ⁻¹	[72]
	Zn/0.4 M Imidazolium-TEMPO	0.06 M ZnCl ₂ , 0.06 M NH ₄ Cl//1 M NaCl	Graphite felt/ Graphite felt	1.65	60/5	97/82.7/80	10.72	1.21	93.4	2	Polybenzimidazole (PBI)/60 mL min ⁻¹	[73]
	Zn/0.5 M 4-TEMPO-NHCOCH ₃	0.3 M ZnCl ₂ , 1 M KCl//1 M KCl	Graphite felt/ Zn Foil	1.63	200/10	95/68/65	13.4	10	90	8.5	Huamo Hangzhou/ 60 mL min ⁻¹	[74]
	Zn/1.5 M MIACNH-TEMPO	1 M ZnCl ₂ , 1 M KCl//1 M KCl	Graphite felt/ Zn Foil	1.71	400/50	99.5/70/70	40.2	36.2	99.2	61.8	Huamo Hangzhou/ 60 mL min ⁻¹	[75]
	Zn/0.2 M DFTEMPO	0.4 M ZnCl ₂ , 1.5 M NH ₄ Cl//2 M NH ₄ Cl	Graphite felt/ Zn Foil	1.64	100/20	98.5/90/89	5.36	5.13	73.7	7.9	NEPEM 1135/30 mL min ⁻¹	[76]
Other	Zn/ 150 g L ⁻¹ PANI	1 M ZnCl ₂ , 1 M NH ₄ Cl	Graphite plate/Zn plate	1.25	32/20	97/ /	■	■	97.9	■	Polypropylene/30 mL min ⁻¹	[65]
	Zn/ 50 mM 1,2-BQDS	1.5 M ZnCl ₂	Carbon felt/ Planar carbon	1.65	12/30	85/88/75	■	■	■	■	Membrane-free/	[77]
	Zn/ 50 mM pBQ	1.5 M ZnCl ₂	Carbon felt/ Planar carbon	1.6	20/30	72/ /	■	■	■	■	Membrane-free/	[68]
	Zn/ 0.1 M FQH ₂	0.1 M ZnO, 4 M NaOH//2.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	Carbon felt/ Carbon felt	2	50/20	99/70/71	5.36	4.5	99.6	8	Nafion 117 and Selemion DSV/ 60 mL min ⁻¹	[69]
	Zn/ 0.05 M HQ	1 M ZnCl ₂ //2.5 M NaCl, 0.1 M HCl	Carbon felt/ Zn fibre	1.1	100/30	90/83/75	■	■	90	■	Membrane-free/	[78]
Fe-based	Zn/ 0.1 M Fe (bpy) ₃ Cl ₂	0.1 M ZnCl ₂ //2 M NaCl	Carbon felt/ Zn foil	1.8	200/1	90/86/77	2.68	■	80	■	Nafion 115/60 mL min ⁻¹	[79]
	Zn/ 1.5 M Fc-SO ₃ Na	1 M ZnSO ₄ //0.5 M Na ₂ SO ₄	Carbon felt/ Zn plate	1.06	60/80	99/70/69	40.2	30	100	25.5	Nafion 117/100 mL min ⁻¹	[80]
	Zn/ 0.2 M Fc1N112-Br	0.2 M ZnCl ₂ , 1 M HCl //1 M HCl	Carbon felt/ Graphite foil	1.4	20/5	96//	5.36	■	■	■	SF600/	[81]
	Zn/ 0.2 M Fc-SO ₃ NH ₄	ZnBr ₂ , 0.5 M NaCl, 0.5 M NH ₄ Cl //0.5 M NaCl, 0.5 M NH ₄ Cl	Graphite felt/ Zinc foil	1.34	100/20	98/85/83	5.36	1.13	92.5	1.53	Nafion 212/	[82]
	Zn/ 1.9 mM P1Fc	0.4 M NH ₄ PF ₆ , 5 mM Zn(PF ₆) ₂ //0.4 M NH ₄ PF ₆ , 5 mM Zn(PF ₆) ₂	Graphite felt/ Zinc foil	1.6	26/0.005	70//	■	■	■	■	Dialysis/20 mL min ⁻¹	[83]
	Zn/ 27 mM PFc (28 °C)	0.1 M ZnCl ₂ , 0.8 M TMACl, 6 mM HCl//0.1 M ZnCl ₂ , 0.8 M TMACl, 6 mM HCl	Graphite felt/ Zinc plate	1.36	> 5/16 ^c	99.25//	■	■	94.5	■	OS-NF-8800/	[66]

^a Q_t, Q_p, Q_i, Q_f are the theoretical, practical, initial and final capacities of the RFBs, respectively.

^b Volume of the negolyte was not considered in the calculation of the energy density.

^c 5 corresponds to the number of days the RFB was operated; 16 corresponds to the current density applied to the RFB with subsequent potentiostatic holding at the cut-off voltages till the absolute current value ≤ 0.5 mA cm⁻².

stirring) to 94%. Due to the low viscosity (7.7 mPa s) of the electrolyte the energy consumption from stirring was negligible compared to the overall operational cost. Additionally, the crossover of the oxidized TEMPO (TEMPO⁺) was prevented by including LiTFSI in the formulation of the electrolyte since, among different anions studied, TFSI showed the strongest interaction with TEMPO⁺ effectively hindering its migration to the negolyte and thereby avoiding capacity fading. TEMPO was also utilized as the posolyte species in a study conducted by Wang

et al., where it was compared to a phenothiazine derivative (C3-PTZ) using propylene carbonate (PC) and acetonitrile (MeCN) as solvents, being TEMPO in MeCN the electrolyte with the highest stability [91]. Notably, operando FT-IR and UV-vis spectroscopies were used to monitor water content in the posolyte and track the signals of the dissolved active species (TEMPO or C3PTZ) (Figure 14 d,e). These analyses revealed that C3-PTZ derivative is significantly more sensitive to water in the posolyte confirming the superior stability of TEMPO-based

Table 4
Summary of the characteristics and performance of published non-aqueous Zn/Organic RFBs.

RFB	Active Species & concentration	Supporting electrolyte (Negolyte//Posolyte)	Electrode +/-	OCV (V)	Cycles/Current density (mA cm ⁻²)	CE/VE/EE (%)	Q _a (Ah L ⁻¹)	Q _p ^a (Ah L ⁻¹)	Q _i /Q _t ^a (%)	E ^b (Wh L ⁻¹)	Membrane/Flow Rate	Ref
Non-Aqueous	Zn/13 mg mL ⁻¹ P1	0.75 M Zn(ClO ₄) ₂ ·6H ₂ O in EC/DMC/DEC (v:v:v 1:1:1)// 0.75 M Zn(ClO ₄) ₂ ·6H ₂ O in EC/DMC/DEC (v:v:v 1:1:1)	Graphite felt/ Zn foil	1.30	500/1 (flow) 1000/1.5 (static)	99/70/70	6.1	0.19	81 (flow)	0.21	Dialysis membrane (MWCO = 1 kDa)/20 mL min ⁻¹	[26]
	Zn/0.01 M PTMA ₄ ·b-P ₅ S ₅	0.75 M Zn(ClO ₄) ₂ ·6H ₂ O in EC/DMC/DEC (v:v:v 1:1:1)// 0.75 M Zn(ClO ₄) ₂ ·6H ₂ O in EC/DMC/DEC (v:v:v 1:1:1)	Graphite felt/ Zn foil	1.30	500/1.5	99.8/65/65	0.268	0.016	95	0.0184	Dialysis membrane (MWCO = 1 kDa)/20 mL min ⁻¹	[84]
	Zn/0.6 M P3	1 M ZnCl ₂ and 0.1 M NaCl in DMF/H ₂ O (1:5 (v:v))//DME/H ₂ O (1:5 (v:v))	Graphite felt	1.4	300/40	/80/	32.16	22.5	80	16	Nafion 212/20 mL min ⁻¹	[85]
	Zn/0.2 M TEMPOL	0.25 M ZnO, 5 M NaOH // 1 M LiPF ₆ , EC (10% (v:v)), DCE (2% (v:v))	Graphite Felt/ Graphite Felt	2.1	100/10	88/55/45	5.36	2	99	2.53	Nafion 117/50 mL min ⁻¹	[86]

^a Q_p, Q_i, Q_t are the theoretical, practical, initial and final capacities of the RFBs, respectively.

^b Volume of the negolyte was not considered in the calculation of the energy density.

Table 5
Summary of the characteristics and performance of published membrane-free Zn/Organic RFBs based on immiscible electrolytes.

RFB	Active Species & concentration	Supporting electrolyte (Negolyte//Posolyte)	Electrode +/-	OCV (V)	Cycles/Current density (mA cm ⁻²)	CE/VE/EE (%)	Q _a (Ah L ⁻¹)	Q _p ^a (Ah L ⁻¹)	Q _i /Q _t ^a (%)	E ^b (Wh L ⁻¹)	Config. Flow/static	Ref
Aq-NAq	Zn/0.1M Fc	1M ZnCl ₂ in H ₂ O // 70%mol Butylacetate + 30%mol Aliquat336	Carbon paper/ Cu foil	1.16 0.1	20/	78/65/51	2.68	0.024	100	■	Static	[89]
	Zn/1.5M TEMPO	Biphasic system (salting-out) 4.6% wt. TEGDME + 6.9% MgSO ₄ + 16.6% LiTFSI + 9.2% ZnSO ₄ 0.5M ZnSO ₄ + 0.3M KPF ₆ in H ₂ O // 0.5M TBAPF ₆ in CH ₂ Cl ₂	Graphite felt/ plate	1.45	150 (63 days)/ 4	99/92/92	40.2 (without stirring)	37.78 (stirring)	100	20	Static + Posolyte stirring	[90]
	Zn/0.5M C8-PTZ	0.5M ZnSO ₄ + 1.8M MgSO ₄ + 0.3M NH ₄ PF ₆ in H ₂ O // 0.5M TBAPF ₆ in MeCN	Graphite felt/ plate	1.6	202/ 11.35	97/80/77	26.8	19.3	79.1	■	Static	[92]
	Zn/0.5M TEMPO	0.5M ZnSO ₄ + 1.8M MgSO ₄ + 0.3M NH ₄ PF ₆ in H ₂ O // 0.5M TBAPF ₆ in MeCN	Graphite felt/ plate	1.56	190/8.54 80/4.27	99/80/80	13.4	12.3	94.5	■	Flow (Posolyte side)	[91]
Aq-Aq	Zn/0.1M FcNCI	WISE Biphasic system (salting-out) 25.5% wt. ZnCl ₂ + 44.9% LiTFSI + 29.6% H ₂ O	Graphite felt/ foil	1.12	30/15 700+200/20	100/36/36	2.68	1.61	96	0.89	Flow (both sides) 15 mL min ⁻¹ 20 mL min ⁻¹	[93]
						100/-/-	2.68	0.83	100	0.62	Static	

^a Q_p, Q_i, Q_t are the theoretical, practical, initial and final capacities of the RFBs, respectively.

^b Volume of the negolyte was not considered in the calculation of the energy density.

posolyte. Thus, the system was based on an aqueous negolyte composed by 0.5 M ZnSO₄, 1.8M MgSO₄ and 0.3 M NH₄PF₆ with a Zn plate while the posolyte consisted of 0.5 M TBAPF₆ in MeCN. Two different concentrations of TEMPO in the posolyte, 0.5 M and 1 M, were tested, and as expected, the battery with the lower concentrated posolyte (0.5 M) performed better. Specifically, this membrane-free Zn/TEMPO battery was cycled over 190 cycles at 8.54 mA cm⁻² (1 C), reaching high coulombic, voltage and energy efficiencies of 99%, 80%, and 80%, respectively, along with 94.5% capacity retention. The capacity utilization reached 91.8%, although significant fluctuations in discharge capacity (50%) were observed during cycling likely due to the use of flowing conditions on the posolyte side. On the zinc side, instabilities may also arise during cycling due to dendrite formation, as no strategies were employed to mitigate this issue, though the authors did not mention any concerns regarding this phenomenon.

Besides TEMPO, other active species investigated as posolyte are phenothiazine derivatives as already mentioned. Chai et al. also studied this family in which C3-PTZ stands out for its high solubility (3.67 M) in the supporting electrolytes although, the derivate C8-PTZ demonstrated the best performance (Figure 14f) [92]. The system of immiscible electrolytes consists of an aqueous negolyte with 0.5 M ZnSO₄ and 0.3 M KPF₆ as supporting salts and a non-aqueous posolyte of 0.5 M TBAPF₆ in dichloromethane (CH₂Cl₂) with 0.5 M phenothiazine derivative dissolved. Despite the use of static conditions and the mass transport limitations that it entails, the battery achieved a relatively high capacity utilization of 72%. The stability of the battery was tested over 202 cycles at 11.35 mA cm⁻² (0.75 C) with a capacity retention of 79.1%. This corresponds to 0.103% cycle⁻¹ capacity fading that was attributed to the gradual dendrite formation over the Zn electrode which is a common drawback in this type of batteries.

5.2. Aqueous-Aqueous immiscible electrolytes

Recently, a new membrane-free Zn/Organic hybrid RFB was reported in which both electrolytes were aqueous-based and tested under flowing conditions simultaneously, becoming the first battery example with these features [93]. Two water-in salt aqueous biphasic electrolytes systems were investigated with different concentrations of salts. The system exhibiting better results was formed by mixing 25.5% wt. ZnCl₂, 44.9% LiTFSI and 29.6% water leading to an upper phase rich in Cl⁻ and acting as negolyte with a Zn foil as electrode and a bottom phase rich in TFSI⁻ with a ferrocene derivative dissolved at 0.1 M concentration as posolyte active species. Initially, the battery was tested under static conditions showing highly stable and efficient performance with no capacity fading and a coulombic efficiency close to 100%. However, after 400 cycles, Zn dendrite formation began to cause fluctuations in the efficiency and after 700 cycles the Zn foil was replaced and the battery recovered its efficient and stable behavior completing over 900 cycles at 20 mA cm⁻² with a capacity utilization of 31.1%. The application of flowing conditions on both electrolytes leads to an improvement in capacity utilization reaching 60% (Figure 14 g). The battery maintained stable performance over 30 cycles with high coulombic efficiency though the energy efficiency was low (36%) mainly due to the high internal resistance caused by the large electrode separation in the reactor. Capacity fading of 4% was observed likely due to ongoing Zn dendrites growth, which, although reduced by the flowing conditions, remains the primary limitation in these batteries.

6. Summary, Challenges and Perspectives

The United States Department of Energy targets to design a stable RFB under a capital cost of US\$ 150 per kWh. The flexibility in the molecular design of organic posolytes can help in the development of an energy-dense RFB with relatively minimal cost constraints. However, a facile synthesis route is desired as the techno-economic issues related to scale-up could increase with more synthesis steps. Coupling organic

molecules with Zn exhibits a lot of advantages such as – lesser toxicity, cost-effectiveness, and robust electrochemistry. In this review, we have assessed different Zn/Organic RFBs as the characteristics of electro-active material, electrolytes, and the cell design.

I. Aqueous Zn/Organic RFBs. Aqueous electrolytes remain the preferred choice due to their high ionic conductivity, organic molecule solubility, and cost-effectiveness, while alternative membranes, such as ion-exchange and size-exclusion, have been explored to lower costs associated with Nafion® membranes. Stability concerns, particularly capacity decay in aqueous organic RFBs, were addressed through synthetic modifications of organic active materials, leading to improved solubility, redox stability, and cycling performance. Key developments included TEMPO-based posolytes with functional groups such as –OH, –SO₃⁻K⁺, and –NHCOCH₃, enabling the electro-active material to achieve practical solubilities exceeding 1 M. The introduction of imidazolium substituent demonstrated exceptional cycling stability with minimal capacity fade over 1000 cycles, while fluorinated-TEMPO (DFTEMPO) improved power density and decreased the susceptibility to molecular degradation. Beyond TEMPO, other organic posolytes, including benzoquinones, ferrocene derivatives, and polymers like PANI and PFC, were investigated. In a specific study using a ferrocene-based posolyte, a redox-targeting strategy with LiFePO₄ was successfully employed to enhance the RFB's energy density. Alternative cell configurations, including single-flow and three-compartment cells, were implemented to simplify system complexity and improve the operating voltage. Despite these innovative designs, they exhibited poor cycling stability.

While the primary focus of most of the RFBs was on optimizing the posolyte, some efforts were made to improve the Zn anode, including the pH adjustment, the exploration of 3D zinc structures to mitigate dendrite formation and enhance zinc electrodeposition. Despite its importance, the extensive characterization of the Zn anode and the impact of detrimental side reactions on the overall stability of corresponding RFBs have been largely overlooked. It is logical to assume that pH changes resulting from the HER on the Zn anode could alter the stability of the catholyte and, in turn, affect the overall stability of the RFB. Although the development of Zn/Organic RFBs is still in its early stages, future research must focus on detailed characterization of the Zn anode. This is essential for bridging the gap between laboratory-scale performance and industrial-scale manufacturing and will be key to their successful commercialization. To accelerate the competitive advantage of Zn/Organic RFBs for commercial applications, it is crucial to apply insights gained from zinc battery research. This includes advancements in zinc anode modifications (such as structured electrodes and surface coatings) and electrolyte engineering strategies (pH, composition, additives) to mitigate HER, dendrite formation, and improve cycling stability.

Future research should prioritize improving the stability of organic active materials through innovative and simple functionalization strategies. These strategies should aim to enhance practical solubility while minimizing chemical and electrochemical degradation. Additionally, optimizing electrolyte compositions is crucial to preventing crossover and extending the overall cycle life of Zn/Organic RFBs. To accelerate the discovery and optimization of high-performance redox-active organic materials, advanced computational techniques such as machine learning (ML), conceptual density functional theory (DFT), and molecular dynamics (MD) can be strategically integrated with experimental methods at the hypothesis formulation stage [62],[94,95]. This synergistic approach enables rapid screening and in-depth understanding of critical performance parameters, including redox potential, solubility, molecular interactions with supporting salts, and degradation pathways. By leveraging these computational tools, researchers can predict structure–property relationships, identify promising molecular candidates, and gain mechanistic insights into stability and reactivity, thereby significantly reducing the trial-and-error efforts in experimental synthesis and characterization. Developing next-generation polymer posolytes with improved solubility can further lower costs by allowing the

use of cheaper membranes while enhancing the energy density of the RFB.

II. Non-aqueous Zn/Organic RFBs are still in infancy and suffer from all basic challenges in general non-aqueous RFBs. The relatively lower solubility of organic molecules (<0.5 M) compared to aqueous solutions (1–3 M), makes the posolyte a capacity limiting side in Zn/Organic RFBs. The solubility issue can be circumvented by finetuning solvent compositions (by using mixture of solvents or by adding miniscule amount of water) as well as by engineering molecular structures (for instance, suitable functionalization) for a particular solvent system. Solubility factor can also be alleviated by redox-active solid boosters as used in redox-targeting flow batteries.

Two important challenges among non-aqueous RFBs are reduced conductivity and increased viscosity even at low concentrations of active materials. Poor ionic conductivity in organic solvents precludes application of higher charge-discharge current density (<20 mA cm⁻²) due to reduced kinetics. Relatively high viscosity not only increases pumping and maintenance cost but also severely affect redox performance due to altered electrode-electrolyte interface and flow dynamics. To overcome these issues, strategies like (a) employing less viscous solvents, like acetonitrile wherever suitable, (b) using additives (like cyclodextrin used in aqueous systems) that can alter molecular interactions or (c) forcing only weaker molecular interactions, such as CH- π interactions, by molecular design as demonstrated by the Hickey group [96],[97], [98]. Another significant issue with non-aqueous RFBs, in general, is the absence of a suitable membrane which can block crossover as effectively as in aqueous systems. Membrane-free Zn Hybrid RFB, using immiscible electrolytes and metallic Zn anode, is a promising solution to avoid crossover while effectively suppresses the inherent self-discharge in non-hybrid membrane-free configurations.

From Zn perspective in organic solvents, high solvation energy barrier reduces Zn-salts solubility in organic solvents and also imposes high charge-transfer resistance resulting in sluggish Zn plating/stripping process. The use of weakly coordinating anions and less viscous solvents such as bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide (TFSI⁻) can not only lower the solvation energy barrier but also enhance the transport properties of Zn²⁺, improving Zn²⁺ dynamic behavior in terms of plating and stripping on the Zn electrode.

III. Membrane-free Zn/Organic RFBs rely on thermodynamic separation of electrolytes, eliminating the need for membranes. The incorporation of Zn-based negolytes effectively reduced self-discharge and enhanced the associated low CEs of these RFBs. However, the primary challenge for achieving long-term cycling stability remains preventing the formation of Zn dendrites. Additionally, while flow conditions have been shown to significantly improve capacity utilization, only one study to date has applied flow conditions to both the negolyte and posolyte sides. In most reported works, either static configurations are used, or flow/stirring is applied solely to the posolyte, with no such conditions on the Zn side. Implementing flow on the Zn side could provide a promising strategy to counteract dendrite growth and further enhance battery performance. Regarding the nature of the electrolytes, while studies involving aqueous–nonaqueous electrolyte combinations have demonstrated superior performance in terms of capacity utilization and energy efficiency compared to those using solely aqueous systems, it is important to consider the environmental implications. The use of toxic organic solvents, such as dichloromethane or acetonitrile, raises significant environmental concerns. Therefore, future research should focus on the development of more sustainable electrolyte combinations, with an emphasis on enhancing both performance and environmental compatibility. Scientific investigations should incorporate complementary techno-economic assessments of Zn/Organic RFBs for grid-scale applications, supported by long-term cycling studies to validate their practical feasibility.

In conclusion, future research on Zn/Organic RFBs should focus on the following aspects to develop them into a safe, stable, and cost-effective long-duration energy storage system.

- Cell voltage – The voltage range of RFBs constrained by the redox potential of organic posolytes must be improved by incorporating novel functional groups [99].
- Practical solubility of the organic posolytes – While various functional groups improved the solubility of organic posolytes, full-cell tests were performed at sub-optimal conditions, necessitating further refinement to determine the optimal electrolyte concentration [100].
- Chemical and electrochemical instability – Organic molecules remain susceptible to decomposition during cycling, resulting in capacity fade and a shortened lifespan. Future molecular designs must focus on developing more robust molecules that resist side reactions, ensuring long-term stability [101].
- Crossover of organic posolytes – The unwanted migration of posolytes across the membrane causes self-discharge, leading to efficiency losses and capacity degradation. Selective membranes that effectively block the crossover of organic molecules while permitting ion transport are still limited [102]. Additionally, molecular designs should be optimized to minimize crossover and enhance battery performance [103].

Figure 15, Table 2

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Athul Seshadri Ramanujam: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Vikram Singh:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Paula Navalpotro:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Nagaraj Patil:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Rebeca Marcilla:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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